

Factors Effecting Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping in Jiangsu Province China

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Abstract

Now a day's online business is growing day by day and satisfies the needs of customers who want to shop online; the present study discussed the e-loyalty, e-services, e-quality, information and social network links which impact on the customer satisfaction towards online shopping in China. There are many companies that are performed their duties and services to sell products and services online and earning handsome amount. In China many companies are active in this business, e.g. Taobao. The present study targets the Jiangsu province companies which are situated in Nanjing, Wuxi, Zhenjiang, Suzhou, Jiangsu province of China. Most of the population of this city shopped online clothing and footwear. However to build up positive and good image in rivalry market is very tough because everyone wants to sell products; it's important to create e-loyalty. E-loyalty is, according to famous researcher's one important ingredient to succeed online and stay profitable. Other important ingredients for e-loyalty are e-satisfaction, e-trust and e-service quality as well as social networks. All of these factors have been investigated and evaluate in which degree they affect customer satisfaction. In this paper, assessed 450 respondents included in the population. The findings have been tested by following statistical analysis, reliability test, correlation analysis, regression analysis and mediation analysis through structural equation modeling. The result showed that e-loyalty is the main driver for customer satisfaction towards online shopping in fashion industry. The result showed that e-service also the main driver for customer satisfaction towards online shopping in fashion industry. The result showed that e-quality and information provide online to create e-loyalty and satisfaction impact customer satisfaction towards online shopping in fashion industry. The result showed that social networks and good relationships are the influence the customer satisfaction towards online shopping in fashion industry. At last the result showed that trust and security playing a mediation role e-loyalty and customer satisfaction towards online shopping in fashion industry. Thereby, a manager should put main focus on what affects satisfaction to increase e-loyalty in this industry.

Keywords: e-loyalty, e-satisfaction, e-quality and information, trust and security, social network, customer satisfaction, online shopping.

1. INTRODUCTION

Research exploring what constitutes the online customer experience is an important area of internet marketing research that requires further exploration. The internet continues to revolutionize the retailing market. Despite the growth in sales in the online retail industry, individual online retailers continue to face severe challenges. They need to create a shopping experience that is as dynamic, exciting, and as emotionally rewarding as shoppers can get from bricks-and-mortar stores as these retailers offer online sales coupled with offline customer service (Li, Zhang, Sun, & Liu, 2018). The multi-channel retailing context gives rise to more transparent information about price and product, empowering consumers to switch to better options. Competing online retailers reside only a few mouse clicks away, so consumers are able to compare competing offers with minimal investments of personal time or effort (Dai, & Jiang, 2016).

The result is fierce price competition and customer loyalty to an e-retailing brand is difficult to obtain. This means it is important to understand consumer online shopping experiences in order to cultivate customer loyalty. Most of the existing research investigating factors influencing online customer experience focuses on

the elements associated with customers' activities in pre-purchase and purchase stages such as features of the retailing website; this includes website design and performance, information quality, ease of use and security (Acheampong et al., 2016). Research has not taken account of the customers' total purchasing experience and failed to pay sufficient attention to the post-purchase stage.

Customer satisfaction has become a determinate for measuring how responsive company products are; hence, has become a vital part of the marketing operations. Marketers tend to place their customers as the pivotal in their business decision making them the most important component of their business activities. In order to increase customer equity, business organizations employ sophisticated procedures in order to maintain and also increase their customer equity, which most scholars believe has a direct connection with the customer satisfaction. According to Yang & Long (2016), customer satisfaction and loyalty are the key elements that determine the success of market concept implementation. Companies when implementing their strategy, look to use the customer reaction as the basis upon which to associate the success of the product. Once the customers are satisfied they tend to repurchase again as well as to influence others also to purchase. Nowadays the Internet plays a critical role in a large and ever-growing array of activities such as communicating, information searching, and entertaining, shopping, and social networking.

According to Qalati et al., (2019), use the term online shopping experience and state that it is 'a complex, holistic and subjective process resulting from interactions between consumers, shopping practices (including tools and routines) and the online environment (e.g., shopping websites, online consumer reviews, and social media)'. As per Zhang, Li, & Zhang (2017), conceptualize a typical online purchase experience as involving multiple web page visits, through which the consumer evaluates the gathered information, before making a purchase. The drawback of these definitions is that they only focus on customer's online interactions and omit possible interactions between e-shoppers and the e-retailers in an offline environment in pre and post-purchase stage, such as interactions between a customer and an e-retailer in physical store when she collects or returns product bought online to the retailer's physical store.

This study seeks to expand our knowledge of consumer online shopping experience, and identify the most important factors from the entire online shopping process that influence student satisfaction. This study fills a gap in research by considering pre-purchase, purchase and post-purchase experience simultaneously. This study also makes several contributions to the e-retailing literature by developing and testing a new model of antecedents and outcomes of the student satisfaction with the entire online shopping process not currently found in the literature. The study also plays significant role in managerial implications on which downstream activities e-retailers should focus on more in order to enhance student satisfaction and lead to student loyalty.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is specifically reviewed in traditional promotional literature Ajay Kaushik, & Potti Srinivasa (2017). Many researchers have looked at the different qualities of this particular element of e-commerce and the way various features affect the outcome of students' satisfaction. Working with the various actions indicating satisfaction and loyalty, researchers can get tempted to establish relationships using online capabilities. According to Hanaysha (2016), links the effect of high- and low-task relevant qualities on satisfaction mediated by means of reactions such as satisfaction and excitement. According to Cristo & Worang (2017), utilized atmospheric factors (e.g., songs and color), termed as low-task pertinent attributes and uncovered two factors that affect participants emotionally, which in turn inspired objectives to purchase.

Tabish Hussain, & Afshan (2017), reviewed a good online site promoting video cameras and identified the interactivity and product information to generally be favorably relevant to customer's satisfaction. Thus, companies need to provide customer's satisfaction in having to create increased human relationships, some of which may not be probable, or having to rely on the loyalty of students'. Nevertheless, if just a tiny percentage of students' would make use of online costs, the possibility could be massive. Using the online cost, a customer can make a lot of financial deals at reduced prices. The world is becoming increasingly open because of the web and the ecommerce industry.

Customer satisfaction is becoming increasingly important. Occasionally, expectations of international students are not met by universities, which may have attracted these customers by overstated and zealous marketing techniques. According to Rather & Sharma (2017), found that a lack of satisfaction was associated with poorer adaptation in international customers. They suggest that the difference between expectations and experiences is associated with overall adaptation: the bigger the discrepancies, the poorer the psychological and socio-cultural adaptation. Research shows that international customers have lower perceptions of services offered by their universities than their domestic counterparts.

Human beings are social and nowadays, consumers are participating in a variety of activities, from consuming content to sharing knowledge, experiences, opinions, and involved in discussion with other consumers online (Chan & Mansori (2016). Today, with the growth of Internet, online social networks have become important communication channels and also virtual communities have emerged. The online world has become a new kind of social communication; connecting people to variety of online communities has been growing during past decade. Groups may never meet in the physical world, but nevertheless they are able to affect behavior including purchasing decisions (Lee et al., 2016). Internet is a social place where created new forum for consumers. Virtual communities, blogs, and online social networking sites provide a platform to influence consumers' purchase decisions.

The online social networks provided facilities for consumers to interact with one another, access information, comments, reviews, and rates that can help them for purchasing decisions in different ways. Online social networks (Facebook, MySpace, Twitter, YouTube, virtual communities, etc.), where individuals as members, construct public profiles to share their knowledge and their experiences, to post information about themselves and have contact with others who exchange and share similar interests (Haghighikhah & Arabi 2016). Online social networks change the way we think about marketing, companies and consumers have direct interaction and relationship with one another. "Much of human behavior is not best characterized by an individual acting in isolation." Nowadays the way of interaction between companies and consumers has been changed and power changed from company to consumer due to online social networking (Kumar et al., 2017).

2.2 E-Loyalty

Building superior customer loyalty is no longer just one of many ways to boost profits. Today it is essential for survival". According to Jeanguenat & Dror (2018), also mean that customer loyalty is essential for a company to survive. To have loyal customers is crucial for companies and that those customers are more worth than the average customer. Those customers are also more profitable. As per Barshan & Aghaei (2017), claim that loyalty is an important issue when it comes to retailing on the Internet. Accordingly, in line with the technology development where more and more business enters the online market, e-loyalty also becomes increasingly important. Due to that, the online competitors are only a few mouse clicks away, makes it even more important in this forum to create customer loyalty.

In addition, Al-dweeri et al., (2017), claim that loyalty is often even more important online than in the physical world and that it is more expensive to acquire new customers online than in the traditional market. He claims that it is understood that "you cannot generate superior long-term profits unless you achieve superior customer loyalty." Additionally, they claim that to gain customer loyalty, companies have to deliver a great experience for the customer. The Internet can be a useful and powerful tool to create stronger customer relationships.

According to Amin (2016), define customer loyalty as "the chance of a customer returning, providing positive word of mouth as well as providing references and publicity for the business." He further discusses that loyalty is about a customer's intention to say positive things about a certain company and recommend it to others — furthermore, their intention to repurchase from that provider in the future. Hence, e-loyalty is specifically defined by (Nisar & Prabhakar 2017) as "the customer's favorable attitude toward an electronic business, resulting in repeat purchasing behavior." Customer e-loyalty can thereby be divided into two parts, which concern the benefits with the customer spreading positive word of mouth and in addition customer's intention to repurchase from the provider in the future.

Rahi & Ghani (2016), claim that another reason why loyal customers are more profitable than regular ones is that those customers are more willing to pay premium prices. Moreover, loyal customers are also more tolerant and understandable when anything goes wrong. Hence, if a company succeeds in creating this customer e-loyalty this will result in an increased profitability. Thereby are these customers valuable for a company. Thereby, to be able to create and increase this customer loyalty online it is important to understand the factors affecting it.

2.3 E-Satisfaction

Satisfaction has generally been presented as an emotional state arising from the non-confirmation of positive or negative initial expectations for the experience of possession or consumption (Nisar & Prabhakar 2017). However, recent research shows that this conception transactional, cognitive, based on a single standard of comparison (initial expectations) is far from sufficient to identify the process of formation of satisfaction. In addition, this definition of popular satisfaction and is often confused with the conceptualization of perceived quality, found no echo in research in the field of ecommerce and the Web sites in general.

This is due to the difficulty of measuring satisfaction from this perspective. In addition, emotional satisfaction has been studied in research on the browsing experience but less evident in research on electronic commerce (Ayo et al., 2016). Current researches mostly opt for design considering the dual satisfaction as the result of two parallel processes, one is cognitive and the other is affective. Beyond this distinction between the cognitive and emotional literature presents another difference in definition of satisfaction. In fact, researchers have defined this concept in two distinct perspectives: a transactional perspective and relational perspectives. The transactional approach this meeting as a state resulting from the subsequent confirmation or refutation of the initial expectations in connection with a transaction.

However, this assessment point seems insufficient to judge the satisfaction felt by the individual during his experiences with the brand or the brand. The relational approach this meeting as "a constructed abstract describes the cumulative experience total (cumulative) consumption of a product or service" (Elbeltagi & Agag 2016). It is thus an effective state resulting from an overall assessment of the relationship with the company. In this way, the move towards relationship marketing requires consideration as an object of satisfaction or dissatisfaction rather than the instant transaction but rather the combined experiences of past consumption.

According to Moriuchi & Takahashi (2016), states that the satisfaction of the user from a tradeoff between rewards and frustrations; for achieving the original purpose of the consultation (or may not be exactly the information sought or only one neighbor), by the way the goal was achieved (in terms of cognitive effort and time involved), the navigation itself, which could provide unintended stimulations. However, it seems important to note that it is difficult for a company to influence the satisfaction derived from a client on the Web. The satisfaction of the latter is also dependent on factors that are not controlled directly by the company (the quality of its equipment, the congestion on the Internet, etc.). In summary, it seems clear that brands and retailers are moving more and more to relational strategies in order to retain customers and maintain and develop relations of exchange and cooperation in the long run.

2.4 E-Service Information and Quality

To succeed and survive in the crowded market a company needs to deliver service quality. Khalifa & Fawzy (2017), claim that this is also true online and that good service quality is crucial for an online retailer to be successful and for their customers to be satisfied. He further defines online service quality as "the extent to which a Website facilities efficient and effective shopping, purchasing, and delivering of products and services." With this definition in mind, it is important for a Website provider not only to facilitate the service for the customer during the visit and purchase point but also in the pre- and the post-stage. Al-dweeri et al. (2017) claim that the evaluation of service quality includes before, during, but also after the purchase was made. Lee & Lin (2001) discuss that online shopping is a process divided into stages, where the customer, in some way or another, performs their purchase. Those stages involve for example navigation on the Website, information search, the transaction, and interaction with the provider. However, the customer does not evaluate

those different stages individually, only a whole. Therefore, it is important that the total experience is perceived positively. Accordingly, the perception of the total e-service quality is important.

2.5 E-Trust and Security

Trust on the seller is actually essential for establishing customer loyalty and having continuity in buyer-seller associations. Many researchers have asserted that trust is usually a vital link that allows relations to be built when there is scepticism, information asymmetry, and anxiety of opportunism (Chen & Zhang 2016) in the case of e-shopping. Any organization that possesses a website in any case undoubtedly tries to minimize risks. High-tech techniques using shields and firewalls may help to stop this kind of fraudulent activity. However, it does not matter how much money or how innovative technology that is being injected into obtaining an online system is, there is not a single sort of factor that has been fully tried and fully trusted upon.

Security concerns are the main opposition to going online as this can drive them to furnish details online. Putting attention exclusively to the probable profit earned with the existing purchase is definitely not an option for the e-retailers. Customers need assurance from the e-retailers on their personal data to be protected. Trust has according to Mehmood et al., (2017), a vital role in the loyalty-building process and is an important driver of e-loyalty. As per Ali & Raza (2017), define trust as “a psychological state composing the intention to accept vulnerability based on expectations of the intentions or behavior of another.” He further discusses that trust includes a person’s total beliefs about how he or she perceives a certain object. They further discuss that in marketing this object can be the brand, the product, the service, any salesperson, but also the place where the product/service being sold, for instance a Website.

Hence, to gain trust is even more important online, where the risk is perceived higher than in the traditional market. It is perceived as risky to do business online since the customer does not have the ability to interact with the company and its staff in the same way as in the offline market. Trust thereby becomes important for an online provider, due to that a customer shopping online might be forced to submit sensitive information such as a credit card number. According to Kasiri, et al., (2017), means that for the customer to receive trust the security risks, privacy and satisfaction are important elements. These parts are also important for the whole Website experience and influence the intention of use.

2.6 Theoretical Framework of the study

Figure 1

- H1): Social network has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction towards online shopping.
- H2) E-Loyalty has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction towards online shopping.

- H3) E-Services have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction towards online shopping.
 H4) E-Service Quality and Information has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction towards online shopping.
 H5) Trust and Security have mediation role between social network, e-loyalty, e-satisfaction, e-services, e-quality & information and customer satisfaction towards online shopping.

3. Methodology

The nature of the study was exploratory and cross-sectional. The method of study was quantitative and investigated with the help of primary data, questionnaire. The overall response of the respondents is positive towards satisfaction. The study has been taken Jiangsu Province cities for data collection and 450 questionnaires were collected, which are properly filled by the customers who shop different products online.

4. Results

Table 1 Reliability Analysis

Variable	No of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
ELO	08	.940
ES	05	.907
TS	04	.885
CS	04	.894
EQI	05	.840
SN	05	.765

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
E-Loyalty	450	13	39	29.98	8.251
E-Services	450	6	20	14.74	4.384
Trust-Security	450	6	20	14.44	3.679
Customer Satisfaction	450	7	20	14.65	4.169
E-Quality and Information	450	8	24	18.43	5.251
Social Network	450	9	24	18.82	3.722

This research study carried out the descriptive statistics using the questionnaire and measured the customer satisfaction towards online shopping in China. The questionnaire for measuring the student satisfaction 5 points Likert Scale is used to collect information from respondent. The scale starts from 1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree. The overall descriptive statistics of all variable is good and satisfaction level of customers is high. The mean and standard deviation also good and fall in the mid of distribution. Table 4.2 represents that mean value of the E-loyalty (EL) is 29.98 and standard deviation is 8.25 which is closer to each other. Mean value of the E-services (ES) is 14.74 and standard deviation is 4.38 which is also closer to each other and has high level of satisfaction. Mean value of the trust and security (TS) is 14.44 and standard deviation is 3.67 which is also closer to each other and has high level of satisfaction. Mean value of the customer satisfaction (CS) is 14.65 and standard deviation is 4.16 which is also closer to each other and has high level of satisfaction. Mean value of the E-quality and information (EQI) is 18.43 and standard deviation is 2.25 which is also closer to each other and has high level of satisfaction. Mean value of the social network (SN) is 18.82 and standard deviation is 3.72 which is also closer to each other and has high level of satisfaction.

Table 3 Correlations Analysis

		ELO	ES	TS	CS	EQI	SN
ELO	Pearson Correlation	1					
ES	Pearson Correlation	.652**	1				
TS	Pearson Correlation	.561**	.482**	1			
CS	Pearson Correlation	.421**	.463**	.530**	1		
EQI	Pearson Correlation	.547**	.639**	.429**	.372**	1	
SN	Pearson Correlation	.610**	.560**	.435**	.391**	.526**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*p<.05, **p<.01 n = Total Respondents = 450, ELO = E-Loyalty, ES = E-Services, TS = Trust and Security, CS = Customer Satisfaction, EQI = E-Quality and Information, SN = Social Network

This research study table 4.3 of correlation is showing the results of the independent and dependent variables of the study. The result of e-loyalty, e-services, customer satisfaction, trust and security, e-quality and information and social network all the variables are positively and significant relationships with each other. E-loyalty and E-services are positively correlated between each other and p are greater than .01 and r = .652. E-Services and Trust and Security are positively correlated between each other and p are greater than .01 and r = .561. Trust and Security Trust and Security and customer satisfaction are positively correlated between each other and p are greater than .01 and r = .421. Customer satisfaction and E-services are positively correlated between each other and p is greater than .01 and r = .463. Customer satisfaction and E-loyalty are positively correlated between each other and p is greater than .01 and r = .547.

E-quality information and e-loyalty are positively correlated between each other and p are greater than .01 and r = .639. E-quality and e-services are positively correlated between each other and p are greater than .01 and r = .429. E-quality and customer satisfaction are positively correlated between each other and p is greater than .01 and r = .372. Social network and e-loyalty are positively correlated between each other and p are greater than .01 and r = .610. E-service and Social networks are positively correlated between each other and p are greater than .01 and r = .560. Customer satisfaction and Social network and are positively correlated between each other and p is greater than .01 and r = .435. E-quality information and social network are positively correlated between each other and p are greater than .01 and r = .391. Social network and E-quality are positively correlated between each other and p is greater than .01 and r = .526.

Table 4 Testing of Hypothesis

		β	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	T	Sig.
H1	SN → SS	.707	.500	.498	198.368	14.084	.000
H2	ELO → SS	.871	.758	.757	620.433	24.909	.000
H3	ES → SS	.815	.663	.662	390.351	19.757	.000
H4	EQI → SS	.746	.557	.555	248.766	15.772	.000

The above table shows results of regression analysis model, accordingly with F value of 198.36 ($p < 0.01$) hypotheses H1 was significant and positive. It represents the fitness of model. Other measures like R square = .500, means that independent variable ‘Social Network’ SN explained 50.0% variation in the dependent variable “Student Satisfaction” SS. Results also explicated that ‘Social Network’ SN has a positive impact on ‘Student Satisfaction SS through standardizing beta value ($p < 0.01$, $\beta = .707$) it shows that one unit increase in Social Network (SN) will bring 70.7% increase Student Satisfaction SS. The individual association of SN with SS is ($p < 0.01$, $t = 14.08$), which is also very considerable. Based on these results of regression analysis, hypothesis H1 was accepted. The above table shows results of regression analysis model, accordingly with F value of 620.33 ($p < 0.01$) hypotheses H2 was significant and positive. It represents the fitness of model. Other measures like R square = .758, means that independent variable ‘E-Loyalty’ ELO explained 75.8% variation in the dependent variable “Student Satisfaction” SS. Results also explicated that ‘E-Loyalty’ ELO has a positive impact on ‘Student Satisfaction SS through standardizing beta value ($p < 0.01$, $\beta = .871$) it shows that one unit increase in E-Loyalty (ELO) will bring 87.1% increase Student Satisfaction SS. The individual association of ELO with SS is ($p < 0.01$, $t = 24.90$), which is also very considerable. Based on these results of regression analysis, hypothesis H2 was accepted.

The above table shows results of regression analysis model, accordingly with F value of 390.35 ($p < 0.01$) hypotheses H3 was significant and positive. It represents the fitness of model. Other measures like R square = .663 means that the independent variable ‘E-Services’ ES explained 66.3% variation in the dependent variable “Student Satisfaction” SS. Results also explicated that ‘E-Services’ ES has a positive impact on ‘Student Satisfaction SS through standardizing beta value ($p < 0.01$, $\beta = .815$) it shows that one unit increase in E-Services (ES) will bring 81.5% increase Student Satisfaction SS. The individual association of ES with SS is ($p < 0.01$, $t = 19.75$) which is also very considerable. Based on these results of regression analysis, hypothesis H3 was accepted.

The above table shows results of regression analysis model, accordingly with F value of 248.76 ($p < 0.01$) hypotheses H4 was significant and positive. It represents the fitness of model. Other measures like R square = .557, means that independent variable ‘E-Quality Information’ EQI explained 55.7% variation in the dependent variable “Student Satisfaction” SS. Results also explicated that ‘E-Quality Information’ EQI has a positive impact on ‘Student Satisfaction SS through standardizing beta value ($p < 0.01, \beta = .746$) it shows that one unit increase in E-Quality Information (EQI) will bring 74.6% increase Student Satisfaction SS. The individual association of EQI with SS is ($p < 0.01, t = 15.77$), which is also very considerable. Based on these results of regression analysis, hypothesis H4 was accepted.

Mediation Analysis

H5: Trust and Security is a mediating role between social network, e-loyalty, e-satisfaction, e-services, e-quality & information and customer satisfaction towards online shopping.

SEM: Path Diagram (Figure 2)

Table 5 Mediation and Direct Effect

Variables	Estimates	S.E	S.E.	C.R	P
SN → TS → CS	.296			7.613	***
ELO → TS → CS	.017		.039	.287	***
ES → TS → CS	.122		.058	1.531	***
EQI → TS → CS	.238		.079	4.153	***
SN → CS	.199		.057	4.944	***
ELO → CS	.460		.040	7.105	***
ES → CS	.127		.065	2.394	***
EQI → CS	.253		.053	3.472	***
TS → CS	.172		.073	3.161	***

Discussion

The study was based on different research questions; those will be discussed and answered in this section. The first question concerned what customer is most influential in the Chinese online fashion industry. The study concludes that the most influential factor is e-loyalty satisfaction. This is also in line with previous research stating that e-loyalty satisfaction is a significant antecedent for customer satisfaction (Tabish Hussain, & Afshan 2017; Rather & Sharma 2017), Meaning, if a customer is satisfied with an online fashion company, there is a great chance that the consumer also becomes loyal. The second most important antecedent for this industry is responsiveness. This relationship has not been evaluated in previous research.

However, this result indicates that if a customer is satisfied with a retailer’s services related to responsiveness, the chances increase that this customer becomes loyal. Thereby, also e-service quality and information is an influential factor for e-loyalty in the online fashion industry. Another important antecedent for

e-loyalty within this industry is trust. This indicates that if a customer trusts a certain fashion e-retailer, it increases the chance for this customer to be converted to be loyal to that company. E-trust has also been evaluated as an important antecedent in previous research (Kumar et al., 2017; Chan & Mansori 2016; Lee et al., 2016). While this study reveals that social networks, e-loyalty, e-services, e-quality information and trust security are most influential ones to enhance the customer satisfaction. Below are these factors affecting e-loyalty summarized and presented. It starts with the most influential factor, followed by the second and third most influential factors identified in this study.

5. Conclusion

After two rounds of data collection, in total 450 completed questionnaires were received, out of which all were from people aged between 18 and 35 and residents of China. Of those 450 respondents, only a few percents never shopped items online, corresponding total of 8 respondents. This number represents almost maximum people when generalizing the result to the population of this study. This implies that almost men and women between 18 and 37 years old are available for shopping online. This is in line with Al-dweeri et al. (2017), who claim that ecommerce has grown and is a giant forum for competition. This opens up a great opportunity for companies operating in e-commerce. In addition, around 85 percent of the population shop clothes and footwear online. Meaning, if generalize the result it implies that people that belong to the group can be expected to purchase clothes and/or footwear online. Moreover, the result showed a high frequency of men and women between 18 and 49 years old are available for shopping online, and for an online company to survive it is according to Amin (2016), important to create a loyal customer. This is essential online since the rivals are only a mouse click away. If a company succeed in create loyal customer it can imply it can result in their own survival, but in particular it can increase a company's profitability. Hence, as mentioned earlier, the purpose of this study was to evaluate the antecedents of e-loyalty in the online fashion industry.

The contributions for a theoretical perspective of this study are several. First, the study has contributed to investigating the antecedents of e-loyalty in a new industry, namely the Chinese online fashion industry. The study has identified what different antecedents are important for e-loyalty in this industry. It could be determined that four significant antecedents which are directly associated with the customer satisfaction towards online shopping. An interesting finding, which the study contributed, was that e-loyalty has a significant influence on student satisfaction. However, all of these antecedents presented have been identified to affect e-satisfaction in previous research. Lastly, for social network and customer satisfaction also has positive sand significant impact on each other. This indicates that company's way to respond to customer's problems, questions and feedback are essential for customer that shop fashion online. If a company succeeds with these services it can result in customer loyalty. This study means instead that e-services, e-quality information and trust, in relative order of importance, are the main drivers for customer satisfaction.

However, e-trust has still a significant role in e-loyalty building, and customer satisfaction almost as important for e-loyalty. From a theoretical perspective this study did also provide some implications for the e-service quality variable. This study identified new relations, namely to measure the e-service quality dimensions direct to e-loyalty. In addition, the e-service quality dimensions came to be changed during the study and thereby a new research model was derived; this is another contribution to the theory. Thereby, a contribution to the theory is that ease of use and Web design can be measured as one variable. Hence, this study conceptualized and measured e-service quality in a new way than previous research.

E-loyalty and customer satisfaction is known as an important phenomenon to be profitable and for survival in the growing online competitive environment. This study has generated a deep insight around the antecedents affecting e-loyalty and other factors important to consider. The investigation has provided useful results, especially for the online fashion market. Both practitioners and academics can benefit from this study and managers can get valuable insight into how to create loyalty online.

Research Implications

This research paper has valuable implications. This section will present implications from both a theoretical perspective and a practical perspective. The first section will present the theoretical implication and the second section will display the managerial implications. This study generated in implications for marketing managers. Apparently, e-loyalty is influenced by customer satisfaction, e-services, e-quality information and social network. However, e-satisfaction is a major driver for customer loyalty in the online fashion industry. Thereby, a manager should put main focus on what affects satisfaction to increase e-loyalty in this industry. It is about arousing positive feelings in the customer and to meet or exceed user's expectations. To acquire a good idea about what the target group wants and appreciate can be a way to increase in e-satisfaction. Additionally, it is also important to focus on what influences responsiveness and customer trust when working with loyalty development.

Hence, managers should strive to improve in their services included in responsiveness to achieve e-loyalty, for instance effective provide assistance for the users, and listen and quickly answer on feedback. In addition, if the company gains customers' trust they will also be able to gain loyalty. However, by trying to reduce the perceived risk, by, for instance improve in security and privacy, and try to affect the customer's total beliefs about how he or she perceives the company and its Website, will most likely improve customer trust and thereby, in the long run, the e-loyalty.

Moreover, there are also influential indirect factors important for a manager to take in to account. Ease of use/ Web design is the main driver for e-satisfaction. Companies can improve satisfaction through improving, for instance, the Web site's design, navigation system on the site and in general try to minimize user effort. By increase satisfaction it indirect influences e-loyalty. The study testifies that the main driver for e-trust is assurance, which is strongly related to security and privacy on a site. Thereby, if a manager strives to increase in e-trust, and by that e-loyalty, they should try to improve the security and privacy elements. Security can be improved by increased safety around fraud and financial loss when customers are doing transactions on their site. Thereby, managers can use this study and tailor their online marketing strategies dependent on their overall objective.

Limitations of the Study

During the process of this study the authors have strived to fulfill the purpose of the study by being consistently accurate to reduce the risk for errors and mistakes. However, no study is faultless and thereby this section will present the limitations occurred throughout the project. A limitation of this study was that every respondent was asked to think about his or her favorite online fashion store when answering the questionnaire. The respondents were thereby evaluating a Website, which they are familiar and satisfied with. This might have implied bias in the investigation. A limitation occurred was during the data collection process, where the authors used an online survey tool. Thereby, a limitation was that it was not possible get as many completed surveys as desire, which affected the total number of responses and indirect also the response rate. During the data analysis process and other limitations occurred. The variable customization had to be excluded from the investigation.

Future Research Directions

After completing this study the researchers have suggestions for further research, which this section will present. This study was based on a quantitative study and a primary suggestion would be to do a qualitative study. This, since it would be interesting to get a deeper and more detailed picture in the field if there are additional factors affecting e-loyalty but also why some antecedents are more important and some are less important for e-loyalty. Further, this study concluded that e-satisfaction is particularly important for e-loyalty and it would be of interest to more detailed determine what factors influence e-satisfaction, e-quality information and social network. Hence, due to that the variable customization was removed from the investigation it would be of interest to try to find a suitable way to measure this variable, since previous research from Rahi & Ghani (2016), has shown that customization has some influence of e-satisfaction. In addition, it would be of interest to test e-service quality as a unit and an own variable to see how it in total

affects e-loyalty, e-satisfaction and e-trust. Thereby, a suggestion for further research is to try to find a way to measure e-service quality as a whole, and not only through the different dimensions. Another interesting insight into the area would be to make a greater comparison between the age and gender and other variables to see if it differs. By identifying if there are differences dependent on demographic factors can help managers to tailor the marketing to be suitable for their target group. The last suggestion for further research would be to investigate in another industry to see if it is the same antecedents.

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